

Next generation of life Saving appliances and systems for saFE and swift evacuation operations on high capacity PASSenger ships in extreme scenarios and conditions

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D9.2 SafePASS Annual Dissemination and Communication Activity Report

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¹ R=Document, report; DEM=Demonstrator, pilot, prototype; DEC=website, patent fillings, videos, etc.; OTHER=other

² PU=Public, CO=Confidential, only for members of the consortium (including the Commission Services), CI=Classified, as referred to in Commission Decision 2001/844/EC

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ACRONYMS AND ABBREVIATIONS

NTUA	National Technical University of Athens
MSRC	Maritime Safety Research Centre
LSA	Life Saving Appliances
CdA	Chantiers de l'Atlantique
TRA	Transport Research Arena
TCD	Trinity College Dublin
M	month
HIMT	Hellenic Institute of Marine Technology
RINA	Royal Institution of Naval Architects
IMO	Maritime Organisation
SOLAS	Safety of Life at Sea COvention
GDPR	General Data Protection Regulation

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Executive Summary

This document constitutes the first annual report on the dissemination and communication activities that were undertaken during the first year of the SafePASS project. Its purpose is to formally outline the outreach of the events and activities and assess their effectiveness in raising awareness of the project's outputs and results amongst the immediate stakeholders, the targeted communities and the general public.

It contains detailed information on events such as conferences, workshops, plenary meetings, and field trips that were organised by the SafePASS team, or which SafePASS partners attended and promoted the project's work and vision. In addition, it contains information regarding the project's social media footprint, the website as well as the publication of scientific papers, newsletters and the project-related information material. Performance monitoring data and audience insights will be presented for all of the SafePASS social media platforms and website.

This deliverable is linked to the SafePASS deliverable D9.1 Dissemination and Communication Plan and provides, beside the abovementioned, updates on the dissemination strategy, insights on the status of reaching the plan's KPIs and the expectations of all the stakeholders.

1 Introduction

1.1 Purpose and Scope

The purpose of this document is to outline, illustrate and analyse the dissemination and communication activities that were undertaken during the first year of the SafePASS project as part of WP9, Task 9.1 Dissemination and Communication. The dissemination and communication activities outlined herein will demonstrate the adherence to the Key Performance Indicators as those specified by SafePASS Annotated Model GA Articles 29 & 38 and will be a reference of the project's status, regarding the project awareness raising , for the consortium members.

More specifically, this document is dedicated to the:

- Presentation of the events, workshops, activities, conferences and professional societies' meetings that were organised or attended within the 1st year of the project
- Development of the dissemination and communication strategy including social media activities, website analytics, issuance of information material and newsletters
- Update of the dissemination and communication strategy

The dissemination and communication strategy and activities were constantly monitored, reviewed and adjusted, throughout the first year of the project, in order to ensure the maximum effectiveness in the visibility and exploitation of the project's outputs. Any deviation from the strategies, activities and/or procedures set by this document will be reported in Chapter 6 including any proposals and suggestions, in order to improve the communication and dissemination strategy plan.

1.2 Intended Readership

This Deliverable is "Public", thus accessible to anyone interested.

It is primarily written for the European Commission (EC) Project Officer (PO) and the consortium members of the SafePASS Project, in order to inform them about the SafePASS dissemination and communication activities that took place within the first year of the project course. More importantly, it serves as an instrument that helps the consortium understand the project's communication objectives and how these could contribute to raising awareness in an efficient and effective way.

Nevertheless, special effort and attention has been given in making this report as a stand-alone document and comprehensible for the general public.

1.3 Document Structure

In the following chapter, an overview of the dissemination and communication strategy will be presented. In Chapter 3, a detailed description of the events and activities organised during this reporting period, is presented. The online footprint of the project is described in Chapter 4, while the information material and the newsletters are presented in Chapter 5. The revision of the dissemination and communication strategy is covered in Chapter 6. The report concludes with the conclusions drawn from the above in Chapter 7.

2 Overview of the Dissemination and Communication Strategy

One of the main focuses of the SafePASS project during the current year was the increase of the project's publicity via various ways. Organisation and participation in events, activities, workshops, conferences and professional societies meetings, being active in social media, publishing scientific papers in Research Gate, updating the project's website and preparing and circulating information material and newsletters, were some of the activities that were included in the dissemination and communication strategy developed in the deliverable D9.1 Dissemination and Communication Plan.

Since every beginning has its own challenges, it was crucial to identify these challenges and start working on them consistently and by taking advantage of all the means available in order to accomplish the targets of the dissemination and communication strategy.

The general overview of the dissemination and communication actions is positive. The SafePASS project organised various successful events and activities, was highly active on social media, increased the visibility of the website, published scientific papers and circulated the first newsletter of the project. It is remarkable that, even though from March 2020 up to August 2020 the unforeseen event of COVID-19 occurred and some of the organised events had to be postponed for the next year, the SafePASS project overcame the challenges and had succeeded mostly its goals. In the following Chapters, a more detailed analysis of the dissemination and communication strategy will be made.

3 Events & Activities

The SafePASS partners represented the project in various exhibitions and conferences and ensured the distribution of the information material produced for such events. Moreover, SafePASS participated in workshops and meetings arranged by the EC and/or proposed by PO.

The SafePASS project had been presented at two conferences/dissemination events and organised three workshops/open events within the framework of different WPs.

In the following Chapters, a detailed analysis regarding the events, meetings and workshops that had been organised during the year, is demonstrated.

3.1 Plenary Meetings

The SafePASS partners organised successfully two meetings where all of the partners had the opportunity to meet each other and discuss about the project. In the following paragraphs a more detailed analysis regarding the plenary meetings will be made along with some photos' presentation.

In addition, the SafePASS project is going to organise the 2nd Plenary Meeting in the upcoming year. The 2nd Plenary Meeting will probably be online, taking into consideration the current and unforeseen circumstances of the pandemic of Covid-19.

3.1.1 Kick-Off Meeting

The Kick-Off Meeting of the SafePASS project was held in Athens, Greece on 10-11th September 2019 and was hosted by the National Technical University of Athens (NTUA). More than 35 representatives from all the 15 consortium partners, were present.

Figure 1. Photo instance from the Kick-off Meeting, 10-11 September, 2019

Figure 2. Photo instance from the Kick-off Meeting, 10-11 September, 2019

3.1.2 1st Plenary Meeting

The 1st Plenary Meeting was held on the 28th January 2020 at the University of Strathclyde (Glasgow, United Kingdom) and was hosted by the Maritime Safety Research Centre (MSRC). The 1st Plenary Meeting was organised to be back-to-back with the first workshop of the project which was held the day after the meeting.

Figure 3. Photo instance from 1st Plenary Meeting in Glasgow, January 28, 2020

3.2 Workshops

During the year, the SafePASS project has organised various workshops. The main aim of the workshops was to develop and analyse certain ship specifications that the project was focused on and to give the opportunity to the consortium members to be trained, exchange knowledge, discuss various issues and learn new safety marine requirements.

The SafePASS project organised the following workshops of which a more detailed analysis will follow in the next paragraphs:

1. “Cruise Ship Evacuation Drills, General Emergency & Safety Training” Workshop
2. “LSA Tank Test Specification” Workshop
3. “The Stakeholder Requirements, LSA & Community Practices” Workshop.

3.2.1 Evacuation Drills, General Emergency and Safety Training Workshop

Consortium members had the opportunity to observe the Pre-Departure Safety Training, Guest Evacuation Drill and All Crew Drill for General Emergency onboard the Royal Caribbean Cruises ‘MV Jewel of the Seas’ cruise ship. Questionnaires and interviews with the safety critical members were critical for the definition of the end user’s requirements. The first workshop took place on 23- 24th November 2019.

Figure 4. Visit onboard RCCL's 'MV Jewel of the Seas' cruise ship, 23-24 November 2019

Figure 5. SafePASS team onboard RCCL's 'MV Jewel of the Seas', 23-24 November 2019

Figure 6. SafePASS team onboard RCCL's 'MV Jewel of the Seas', 23-24 November 2019

3.2.2 LSA Tank Test Specification Workshop

Academic members of the consortium together with the Life-Saving Appliances (LSAs) manufacturers met in Chantiers de l'Atlantique (CdA) shipyard in order to plan the LSA's parameters for model testing. The workshop took place on 11th December 2019. As a result of the workshop, the testing scenarios were defined based not only on existing LSA models but also on new concepts for deployment. This meeting also concluded to the agreement of initiating the contacts for collaboration with FLARE Project (another Horizon 2020 funded project).

3.2.3 The Stakeholder Requirements, LSA and Community Practices Workshop

The workshop, which was organised on 29th January 2020, in Glasgow, was dedicated to the passenger ship safety and emergency response. Consortium members and external representatives from Flag states, Classification Societies and Cruise Ship Operators participated in an open discussion and helped the consortium to focus on its research efforts.

Figure 7. Photo instance from Stakeholder Requirements meeting, January 29, 2020

Figure 8. Photo instance from Stakeholder Requirements meeting, January 29, 2020

3.3 Conferences and Professional Societies Meetings

During the first year of the project, the project results were disseminated in a number of conferences and workshops. The details are given in the following paragraphs.

3.3.1 General Assembly of Greek Cruise Ship Owners Union

The meeting was scheduled on 8th December 2019 on board the cruise ship 'CELESTYAL CRYSTAL'. SafePASS partner, RINA Hellas attended the meeting and disseminated SafePASS project's aim and objectives. Present in the assembly were also representatives from the DNV GL and BV classification societies as well as from the Hellenic Ministry of Shipping and Island Policy and from the Hellenic Ministry of Tourism. Amongst the issues that were discussed were the current regulatory developments for passengers' ships and the effect of technological innovations in ship safety.

3.3.2 RINA Scottish Branch Meeting

A successful meeting was organised on 2nd March 2020 by the academic partners from the University of Strathclyde. During that meeting, they presented their research work and made an introductory presentation of the SafePASS project in Badcock International Rosyth Shipyards after an invitation by the Scottish Branch of the Royal Institution of Naval Architects.

Figure 9. Photo instance from RINA Scottish Branch meeting, March 2, 2020

3.3.3 Sustainable and Safe Passenger Ships Conference

This [conference](#), which was held on 4th March 2020, in Athens was co-organised by the Hellenic Institute of Marine Technology and the Royal Institution of Naval Architects. The academic partners from National Technical University of Athens (NTUA) and MSRC presented their technical papers related to ship evacuation.

Figure 10. Photo instance from HIMT and RINA conference, March 4, 2020

Figure 11. Photo instance from HIMT and RINA conference, March 4, 2020

Figure 12. Photo instance of VIPs from HIMT and RINA conference, March 4, 2020

3.3.4 Transport Research Arena (TRA2020)

The [Transport Research Arena](#) is the largest European conference for research and technology developments on the fields of transport and mobility. The TRA conference is being held in a different European city every two years and it attracts presenters and attendees from a wide range of industries, research institutions, public sector organisations and news agencies. This year, the 8th TRA was to take place in Helsinki from 26/04/2020-30/04/2020 but it was cancelled due to the COVID-19 pandemic.

Members of the SafePASS consortium had submitted a conference paper and a poster to capitalise on the conference's opportunities for dissemination and communication of our project's vision and strategy in addressing maritime accident response. The cancellation of the TRA2020 was a significant drawback on the consortium's efforts to raise awareness about SafePASS project.

Nevertheless, since the SafePASS submissions were peer reviewed and accepted, the authors of the paper were informed that they retain their right to cite their work. Considering the above, the conference paper was made publicly available via ResearchGate and was disseminated via our project's social media and website.

SafePASS – Transforming Marine Accident Response

Paper ID1184

Evangelos Boulougouris; *University of Strathclyde*; Dracos Vassalos; *University of Strathclyde*; Fotios Stefanidis; *University of Strathclyde*; Gianni Karaseitanidis; *National Technical University of Athens*; Lazaros Karagiannidis; *National Technical University of Athens*; Angelos Armditis; *National Technical University of Athens*; Nikolaos Ventikos; *National Technical University of Athens*; Dimitris Kanakidis; *EXUS Software Ltd.*; Dimitris Petrantonakis; *EXUS Software Ltd.*; Paul Liston; *Trinity College*

SafePASS Objectives

Ship evacuation is the last line of defense in case of extreme fire or flooding emergencies onboard. The current assumptions behind the conventional evacuation procedures and life-saving appliances (LSAs) are often challenged and criticised as insufficient, especially for large capacity passenger vessels.

SafePASS is an EU H2020 programme that brings together 15 European partners from industry, academia and classification societies. It started in Sep 2019 and it has a duration of 3 years. The aim of the consortium is to **radically redefine the evacuation processes, systems and equipment's in order to make the overall emergency response safer and more efficient in all environments, hazards and weather conditions, independently of the demographic factors.**

The SafePASS vision and plan for a safer, faster and smarter ship evacuation involves:

- The integration of 'smart' technology and Augmented Reality (AR) applications to provide individual guidance to passengers towards the optimal route of escape based on their demographic characteristics and the hazard (flooding or fire).
- The design of the next generation of life-saving appliances.
- A holistic and seamless approach to evacuation, addressing all states from alarm to rescue.

SafePASS Ecosystems

The high-level architecture of SafePASS integrates the following ecosystems:

Next Generation of life-saving appliances

NG LSAs will be designed and developed to ensure safe mustering and abandonment operations under extreme weather conditions and hazards on-board.

Smart Environment Elements

SafePASS Personal Survival Equipment (PSEs) will enable personalized evacuation route based on mobile 'smart' devices and physiological monitoring.

SafePASS Core Platform

It will provide in real-time **Location-based Dynamic Evacuation Route (LDER)** for the entire ship and all the users using a Crowd Modelling Server.

Risk Modelling Tool (RMT)

RMT will integrate existing numerical simulation tools for fire and flooding, and perform risk analysis in real-time for the purposes of estimating the Potential Loss of Life providing decision-support to the decision-makers.

SafePASS Special Features

- The modular integration of the SafePASS subsystems enables gradual and efficient implementation and easy upgrade.
- SafePASS System is designed to be **passenger-centric, user-friendly** so that it can address individual needs.

- The passenger's demographic characteristics (e.g. gender, age), mobility issues, vital semantics and current location will be available to the emergency response team.
- Hazard related sensor readings will provide an real-time picture of the current and projected states as the emergency develops.
- Crowd dynamics algorithms will process the aforementioned data and calculate the LDER.
- The Common Operational Picture and the AR application will provide on spot guidance to the crew, thus reducing the Human Error Probability

Conclusions

SafePASS will increase safety onboard ships by integrating 'smart' technologies in the life-saving appliances, by improving their design and availability and by developing a tool that will evaluate the risk and the potential casualties in real-time based on readings from sensors monitoring the hazard propagation and passenger location. The SafePASS core-platform will then provide the decision makers with actionable recommendations and guide passengers and crew accordingly.

Acknowledgements

The SafePASS project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 Research and Innovation programme under the Grant Agreement No. 815146. The opinions expressed herein are those of the authors and the European Commission is not responsible for any use that may be made of the information it contains.

More information

- www.safe-pass-project.eu
- [@SafePASS_H2020](https://twitter.com/SafePASS_H2020)
- info@safe-pass-project.eu
- [@company/safe-pass-project](https://www.linkedin.com/company/safe-pass-project)
- [SafePASS.H2020](https://www.facebook.com/SafePASS.H2020)
- [@SafePASS.H2020](https://www.instagram.com/SafePASS.H2020)

traconference.eu #TRA2020 #rethinkingtransport @TRA_Conference

Figure 13. Transport Research Arena 2020 ePoster

4 Online Footprint

The SafePASS project team used to the maximum all the available social media means with the main purpose to increase the publicity of the project. The contents of the social media accounts were updated on a regular basis. In addition, an online network of circulations was created with the main purpose to increase the visibility and the followers of the SafePASS social media. The focus of the circulations was the promotion of the SafePASS project and activities as well as to inform the general public on issues that are within the thematic scope of the project.

The outcome was positive and the reactions to the circulations were impressive. During the 1st year, the visibility of the project's website, the LinkedIn page, the Facebook page and the Twitter account was increased. Additionally, the followers in the abovenamed social media were increased massively comparing the numbers to the initial stage.

In the following Chapters, an analysis of the SafePASS project's activities in the social media with graphs will be presented.

4.1 Social Media Activity

The SafePASS project's social media accounts have been active since M01 and are updated with new content on a regular basis. The social media accounts include Twitter, LinkedIn, Facebook and Research Gate.

4.1.1 Twitter

The project's [Twitter](#) account is quite active. Since October 2019, the followers have been increased from 34 to 201. The following analytics present the great increase of the followers.

Table 1: Tweeter KPIs Status Summary

Tweeter Status in relation to KPIs			
Followers	KPI for Year 1	Status for Year 1	KPI for Year 3
201	≥100	+101%	≥300

Figure 14. Tweets from SafePASS account

4.1.1.1 3.1.1.1 Analytics

Twitter allows the monitoring of the number of times that a tweet has been seen (Impressions) and provides an insight on the percentage of the viewers that have interacted with the tweet (Engagement Rate).

Table 2: Twitter Analytics Summary (May- July) [Source: Twitter]

01 May 2020- 30 July 2020				
Total Impressions	Highest Engagement Rate	Link Clicks	Retweets	Likes
11.7K	16.5%	35	36	140

Figure 15. Twitter Impressions May- July [Source: Twitter]

Table 3: Twitter Analytics Summary (February- April) [Source: Twitter]

01 February 2020- 30 April 2020				
Total Impressions	Highest Engagement Rate	Link Clicks	Retweets	Likes
12.1K	7.5%	14	11	41

Figure 16. Twitter Impressions February- April [Source: Twitter]

Table 4: Twitter Analytics Summary (November- January) [Source: Twitter]

01 November 2019- 30 Jan 2020				
Total Impressions	Highest Engagement Rate	Link Clicks	Retweets	Likes
10.2K	9.5%	21	54	121

Figure 17. Twitter Impressions November- January

4.1.2 LinkedIn

A [LinkedIn](#) page was created for the project in order to engage the professional communities that are interested in maritime safety related topics. The community hashtags of the page (#cruiseships, #safety, #H2020) were chosen strategically so as to portrait the project’s area of operation while also being generic enough to allow exposure to a wider range of audience.

The circulations on the LinkedIn page are made on a regular basis. According to the Analytics (presented in subparagraph 3.1.2.1), the visibility of the page had an increase. Additionally, the followers were increased to 349. Even though the increase

in the followers' number in the SafePASS LinkedIn account is foreseen in the GA, it should be highlighted that the followers gained, are people whose scientific interest matches with the qualities of the SafePASS project. This can be identified by the likes gained in each of the posts and by the re-circulations of the posts by several followers.

Table 5: LinkedIn KPIs Status Summary [Source: LinkedIn]

LinkedIn Status in relation to KPIs				
Followers	KPI for Year 1	Status for Year 1	KPI for Year 3	Status for Year 3
374	≥100	+274%	≥300	+24.7%

SafePASS Project Admin view

Home Career Pages Content **NEW** Analytics Activity

Posted by Fotios Stefanidis • 6/25/2020 • Sponsor now

SafePASS Project
349 followers
2w •

#Maritime #accidents indicate gaps in maritime **#safety**. **#SafePASS** aims to spearhead worldwide the next generation of **#LifeSaving** Appliances and Systems for safe and swift **#evacuation** operations on high capacity ...see more

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Abstract

The evacuation of a ship is the last line of defence against human losses in case of emergencies in extreme fire and flooding casualties. Since the establishment of the International Maritime Organisation (IMO), Maritime Safety is its cornerstone with the Safety of Life at Sea Convention (SOLAS) spearheading its relentless efforts to reduce risks to human life at sea. However, the times are changing. On one hand, we have the new opportunities created with the vast technological advances of today. On the other, we are facing new challenges, with the ever-increasing size of the passenger ships and the societal pressure for a continuous improvement of maritime safety. In this respect, the EU-funded Horizon 2020 Research and Innovation Programme project SafePASS, presented herein, aims to radically redefine the evacuation processes, the involved systems and equipment and challenge the international regulations for large passenger ships, in all environments, hazards and weather conditions, independently of the demographic factors. The project consortium, which brings together 15 European partners from industry, academia and classification societies, the SafePASS vision and plan for a safer, faster and smarter ship evacuation involves: i) a holistic and seamless approach to evacuation, addressing all states from alarm to rescue, including the design of the next generation of life-saving appliances and; ii) the integration of 'smart' technology and Augmented Reality (AR) applications to provide individual guidance to passengers, regardless of their demographic characteristics or hazard (flooding or fire), towards the optimal route of escape.

(PDF) SafePASS -Transforming Marine Accident Response
researchgate.net

17

Like Comment

Figure 18. LinkedIn posts from SafePASS account [Source: LinkedIn]

4.1.2.1 Analytics

LinkedIn provides the most insightful analytics especially with regards to the visitor demographics. The graphs below depict the project's page visitors and followers over the first 11 months of the project and identify the distributions of various stakeholder groups.

Figure 19. LinkedIn new Followers per month [Source: LinkedIn]

Figure 20. LinkedIn Impressions per month [Source: LinkedIn]

As it is evident from the graph below, most of our views are being from a mobile device. This suggests that the content of our posts should always be presented in such a way that it is friendly to the people accessing it from a mobile device.

Figure 21. LinkedIn Viewers per month [Source: LinkedIn]

Despite the focus of SafePASS to the Maritime industry, the visitor metrics indicate that the largest portion of our visitors comes from the Telecommunications industry. This could be attributed to the relative size difference between the Maritime and Telecommunications industry. It is expected that at a later stage of the project, the page posts will be about the evacuation related research outputs and the new Life-Saving Appliances the Maritime, Research and Higher Education industries will have increase their share on the visitor distribution chart.

Figure 22. LinkedIn Viewers: Industry Distribution [Source: LinkedIn]

Figure 23. LinkedIn Viewers: Job Function Distribution [Source: LinkedIn]

Figure 24. LinkedIn Viewers: Seniority Level Distribution [Source: LinkedIn]

Over the next 2 years, special effort will be made in order to diversify the viewers' location distribution. The content of some of the posts will be adjusted so that to attract more visitors from the continental Europe and the SafePASS partner's will be asked to direct visitors from their local social media accounts to the project's page in a more consistent and systematic way.

Figure 25. LinkedIn Viewers: Location Distribution [Source: LinkedIn]

Figure 26. LinkedIn Viewers: Company size Distribution [Source: LinkedIn]

4.1.3 Facebook

The SafePASS Facebook page has managed to obtain 155 followers, something which is quite positive but it is simultaneously something that needs to be improved. However, taking into consideration that Facebook is made up of a different audience than the other social/professional networks, it is something which is accounted for in the analytics that were collected.

The audience of the Facebook page reacted satisfactorily in the circulations which were being made on a regular basis.

Table 6: Facebook KPIs Status Summary [Source: Facebook]

Facebook Status in relation to KPIs			
Followers	KPI for Year 1	Status for Year 1	KPI for Year 3
151	≥100	+51%	≥300

Figure 27. Facebook posts from SafePASS account [Source: Facebook]

4.1.3.1 3.1.3.1 Analytics

The Facebook analytics suggest a significant clustering of visitors from mainly two countries, Greece and the UK. It is therefore important that over the next year effort to be put in creating a normal distribution in terms of visitors' location. One of the measures to achieve this will be via the more systematic dissemination of the Facebook page through our partners social media so as to attract visitors from their corresponding countries.

Figure 28. Facebook Page Followers [Source: Facebook]

Figure 29. Facebook Page Reactions, Comments and Shares [Source: Facebook]

Figure 30. Facebook Page Views per month [Source: Facebook]

Figure 31. Facebook Page Follower Demographics [Source: Facebook]

4.2 Scientific Publications - ResearchGate

One of the core research outputs of the project is the open access to publications in the form of journal/conference papers as well as whitepapers. This form of dissemination targets specific scientific and industrial stakeholders.

The publication of scientific papers was a task which was carried out preliminary by the academic partners of SafePASS, namely NTUA, MSRC and TCD. The SafePASS project successfully published three Articles which were published in Research Gate, namely: a. Modern Trends in Ship Evacuation; b. A critical review of the evacuation Process; c. SafePASS- Transforming Marine Accident Response. The reaction on the scientific audience was quite impressive. Some of the Articles had more than 340 readers.

Additionally, all the published Articles in Research Gate were circulated in all the project’s social media accounts in order give publicity to the SafePASS’s project.

In the following paragraphs, a more detailed analysis will demonstrate the content of each of the Conference Papers separately along with their analytics.

4.2.1 ‘Modern Trends in Ship Evacuation’ Conference Paper

An interesting Article titled ‘Modern Trends in Ship Evacuation’ was written and published by MSRC. Accidents such as the Costa Concordia and more recently the Viking Sky incident cause a societal pressure for improving safety and emergency response in passenger ships. Finding realistic solutions for improvement requires first and foremost an understanding of the current regulatory landscape and the corresponding performance assessment standards. The first part this paper was dedicated to the provision of a comprehensive outline of the regulatory framework that will ensure compliance of any new system and model developed. The second part was dedicated on the state-of-art projects and novel ideas on ship evacuation analysis and Life Saving Appliances (LSAs) for the purpose of unveiling areas of improvement. Finally, having identified the gaps in the topics, suggestions were made on how future work can address the challenges of marine accident of marine accident response.

Place: Sustainable and Safe Passenger Ships Conference, Athens, Greece

Date: March 2020

4.2.1.1 Analytics

Table 7: ResearchGate Analytics: Conference Paper No.1 [Source: ResearchGate]

Conference Paper No.1			
Research Interest	Citations	Recommendations	Reads
4.4	0	1	93

The Research Interest score of 4.4 places the publication higher than 64% of the research items on ResearchGate. This metric is based on the number of citations, recommendations and reads by ResearchGate members.

4.2.2 ‘A critical review of the Evacuation Process’ Conference Paper

The Article titled ‘A critical review of the Evacuation Process’ was written and published by National Technical University of Athens (NTUA). The Article was focused on ship evacuation in response to fire or flooding hazards which both involve two phases mustering, that is the reallocation of passengers from a designated area to a safer area or to the muster stations and abandoning the ship (embarkation and launching lifeboats). Evacuating a dynamic and complex environment such as a cruise vessel is a safety-critical and strictly time-bound task, which typically involves thousands of people moving within parts of the ship, assisted by a significant number of crew personnel, and a complicated decision- making process based on the evolving situation on-board and the information available to the decision makers. Timely and safe mustering and abandonment require accurate evacuation of ship’s conditions as well as estimation of remaining time. A critical review of the evacuation process due

to fire or flooding from Cruise Vessels and large RoPax Vessels in terms of the existing regulatory framework, the installed life-saving appliances and the smart environment elements are presented. This paper was concluded with the future challenges and development concerning the evacuation process.

Place: Sustainable and Safe Passenger Ships Conference, Athens, Greece

Date: March 2020

3.2.2.1 Analytics

Table 8: ResearchGate Analytics: Conference Paper No.2 [Source: ResearchGate]

Conference Paper No.2			
Research Interest	Citations	Recommendations	Reads
1.5	0	0	48

The Research Interest score of 1.5 places the publication higher than 42% of the research items on ResearchGate.

4.2.3 'SafePASS-Transforming Marine Accident Response' Conference Paper

The Article titled 'SafePASS-Transforming Marine Accident Response' which was written and published by MSRC was about the transforming marine accident response. The evacuation of a ship is the last line of defence against human losses in case of emergencies in extreme fire and flooding casualties. Since the establishment of the International Maritime Organisation (IMO), Maritime Safety is its cornerstone with the Safety of Life at Sea Convention (SOLAS) spearheading its relentless efforts to reduce risks to human life at sea. However, the times are changing. On one hand, we have the new opportunities created with the vast technological advances of today. On the other, we are facing new challenges, with the ever-increasing size of the passenger ships and the societal pressure for a continuous improvement of maritime safety. In this respect, the EU-funded Horizon 2020 Research and Innovation Programme project SafePASS, presented in this Article, aims to radically redefine the evacuation processes, the involved systems and equipment and challenge the international regulations for large passenger ships, in all environments, hazards and weather conditions, independently of the demographic factors. The project consortium, which brings together 15 European partners from industry, academia and classification societies. The SafePASS vision and plan for a safer, faster and smarter ship evacuation involves: i) a holistic and seamless approach to evacuation, addressing all states from alarm to rescue, including the design of the next generation of life-saving appliances and; ii) the integration of 'smart' technology and Augmented Reality (AR) applications to provide individual guidance to passengers, regardless of their demographic characteristics or hazard (flooding or fire), towards the optimal route of escape.

Place: TRA 2020, Helsinki, Finland

Date: April 2020

4.2.3.1 Analytics

Table 9: ResearchGate Analytics: Conference Paper No.3 [Source: ResearchGate]

Conference Paper No.3			
Research Interest	Citations	Recommendations	Reads
6.6	0	0	343

The Research Interest score of 6.6 places the publication higher than 72% of the research items on ResearchGate.

4.3 Website

All the necessary provisions (allocation of resources) have been made in regards to the project's website related tasks. The SafePASS [website](#) is the main media tool for communicating and disseminating the project's related material. Its modern design and aesthetics aim to spark the interest of the visitors whilst regular updates on its content and functionalities ensure the highest possible quality and efficiency of the communication and dissemination objectives.

As of the 25th of May 2018, EU's General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) has become enforceable and acts as a mandate for clear and careful acquisition, storage and handling process of personal information. In the light of this, SafePASS partners as a whole but more importantly those who lead the Ethics Requirements (WP10), the Dissemination and Communication activities (WP9) and designing/managing the website (EXUS) ensured adherence to the current regulations regarding the website's cookies policy or other implications rising from the GDPR. For that purpose, they requested information from the relevant departments, and they prepared proper cookies and privacy policy.

Additionally, as mentioned previously the website has been updated on a regular basis. All of the dissemination material that was produced within the first year of the project, the first SafePASS newsletter, the first SafePASS press release, the SafePASS survey as well as all the events and conferences in which the consortium participated, were published on the website. It is highlighted that the SafePASS team created a friendly website in order to approach various individuals from different areas of interest. The users have the opportunity to subscribe in the mailing list of the project in order to receive updates and/or any other material and/or the newsletters that are published in the website.

4.3.1 Analytics

The website analytics indicate that there is a significant clustering of our visitors in terms of their location. More specifically, 46% of our website viewers are from Greece, 32% from the United Kingdom whereas the total portion of viewers from 35 other countries is just 22%. This suggests that any future communication and dissemination actions should try to diversify their target audiences in terms of their location. In terms of traffic by month, there was a significant increase of visitors during May and July which is probably associated with the publication of the first SafePASS newsletter and a conference attendance. The social media posts directed the viewers to the news sections of our website thus increasing the traffic.

Table 10: Website Traffic: Viewers Distribution by Location [Source: Google Analytics]

Website Traffic by Country		
Greece	United Kingdom	Other
46%	32%	22%

Figure 32. Website Visitors by Country [Source: Google Analytics]

Figure 33. Website Views November-July [Source: Google Analytics]

Figure 34. Website Unique Visitors November-July [Source: Google Analytics]

For more a more detailed insight on the number of visitors in the website please refer to the corresponding table in the Annex section of this report.

5 Information Material & Newsletters

Other types of one-way communication tools employed were the SafePASS leaflet, the roll-up banner and the factsheet. This information material is designed according to the brand identity of the project and conveyed the information about the vision, objectives and impact of SafePASS project.

The informational material has been finalised during the 1st year of the project and is available via a dedicated Redmine folder for printing so as all partners can use it in several events and conferences in order to disseminate the project’s aim and objectives. The general public can download the information material from the website by going to the corresponding dedicated section in SafePASS.

5.1 Leaflet

The final version of the leaflet is an informative leaflet which contains all the required information about the project. A leaflet which can addressed to anyone who may be interested in the project, written with a plain language without complicated and scientific terms.

It includes important information and details about the project’s main results as well as the goals and objectives of the project. Moreover, it presents the SafePASS consortium, the contact details of the Project Coordinator, the Project Manager and the Dissemination Manager of SafePASS, a QR code which leads to the official project’s website and the relevant social media accounts.

Next generation of life Saving appliances and systems for safe and swift evacuation operations on high capacity PAssenger ships in extreme scenarios and conditions

Partners

SafePASS consortium, coordinated by the National and Technical University of Athens, brings together 15 partners from the industry, academia and classification societies from all over Europe. They all share the vision of making ship evacuation and abandonment smarter, faster and safer.

We Are Social

- www.safepass-project.eu
- info@lists.safepass-project.eu
- SafePASS Horizon2020
- @SafePASS_H2020
- SafePASS Project
- @SafePASS.H2020

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The project has received funding from the European Union's H2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 815146. The content of this material reflects only the author's view and the European Commission is not responsible for any use that may be made of the information it contains.

Figure 35. SafePASS Leaflet

5.2 Roll-up Banner

The roll-up banner includes information similar to the information mentioned in the leaflet. However, it is mainly focused on the outcomes of the project. The social media accounts are included in the banner so that anyone who may be interested in the project will be able to follow. Finally, a QR code that leads to the official website of the project is also included. The banner is intended to be used in conferences, exhibitions, seminars and workshops that SafePASS partners will participate in.

Figure 36. SafePASS roll-up banner

5.3 Factsheet

The factsheet is intended and addressed to any sponsor and/or organisation and/or authority and/or even individuals who are interested in the project. The factsheet also includes information about the partners, social media accounts and general information about the project in a very plain and clear way, without many details, so that the individual who reads it finds out the most important facts of the project quickly.

Description

SafePASS solution, will radically redefine the evacuation processes, evacuation systems and international standards for passenger ships in all environments by developing a combination of innovative systems that will collectively monitor, process and inform during emergencies both safety personnel and passengers of the optimal evacuation routes, coupled with advanced, intuitive and easy to use Life-Saving Appliances (LSAs) that go beyond the current state-of-the-art.

Main Outcomes

- ✓ SafePASS Smart Environment Element
- ✓ SafePASS Core Platform
- ✓ SafePASS Next Generation Life-Saving Appliances
- ✓ SafePASS Evacuation Risk Modelling Tool

www.safepass-project.eu

info@lists.safepass-project.eu

The project has received funding from the European Union's H2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 815146. The content of this material reflects only the authors' view and the European Commission is not responsible for any use that may be made of the information it contains

@SafePASS_H2020

SafePASS Project

@SafePASS.H2020

SafePASS Horizon2020

At a Glance

Facts and Figures

Funded Under: H2020

Total Budget: €8,270,366

Duration: 3 years (Sept 2019 - Aug 2022)

Consortium: 15 partners from 8 EU countries

Coordinated By: National Technical University of Athens (NTUA), Greece

Partners

Figure 37. SafePASS factsheet

5.4 Newsletters

The first newsletter of the project was published on the project's website in April 2020. The newsletter contained all the information regarding the activities of the SafePASS project along with its participation in conferences, events and workshops and some upcoming events.

It is highlighted that the 1st newsletter covered activities performed only in the first 7 months and not the full year of the project's lifetime. The reason is because all the upcoming events were postponed due to the unfortunate event that affected the global, Covid-19. Nevertheless, the newsletters will be prepared and published on a regular basis every 6 months. All the newsletters will be available online via the project's corresponding [webpage](#), will be circulated through the SafePASS social media and will be sent via email to the registered subscribers.

First 7 months at a glance...

April 2020 | e-Newsletter

This is the first newsletter of the SafePASS project and contains information about the most important events related to SafePASS project up to date.

The duration of the project is three years, starting from September 2019.

What is SafePASS Project about ?

Aim

SafePASS is an EU H2020-funded project that aims to the design of the next generation of life-saving appliances and systems for safe and swift operations on high capacity passenger ships in extreme scenarios and conditions.

[Click here to find out about the SafePASS Objectives and much more](#)

Consortium Meetings

Kick-Off Meeting | 10-11 Sep 2019

Figure 38. [SafePASS Newsletter No.1](#)

6 Dissemination and Communication Future Plans

In the first half of the year, the SafePASS project was within the proposed dissemination and communication strategy, described in the deliverable D9.2 SafePASS Dissemination and Communication Plan. However, during the second half of the year the plans had to change slightly. Due to the current pandemic of COVID-19, all the upcoming events were postponed. The SafePASS consortium tried to overcome the challenges appeared during the pandemic and continued the hard work remotely. The SafePASS project, under these strange circumstances, tried to focus on online promotion of the project by publishing scientific articles in the social media, organising workshops and webinars online. A more detailed analysis will follow in the following paragraphs.

6.1 Social Media Activity Plan

Taking into consideration the current year regarding the project's activities in social media and by gaining some experience on that, the SafePASS project is more well-prepared to outline a more efficient social media activity plan.

Firstly, the circulations on the social media accounts will be more organised and targeted to the audiences. A plan about the exact day and the content of the circulations shall be agreed at the beginning of each week depended on the material that the project has to circulate. The SafePASS project will continue to get connected with individuals who are interested in the project and individuals who would like to learn more about the project. In addition, through the circulations, we will encourage the audience to re-circulate the dissemination material with their audience in order to increase the SafePASS followers and to increase the publicity of the project.

Finally, short videos are being prepared by the partners and associates of the consortium in order to describe the SafePASS project in a more interactive way. With the short videos, the audiences will have a more interactive experience with the project. It is notable that, the distribution of short videos is an easy way to be circulated by the partners, followers, some associations with the purpose to, again, increase the publicity of the project.

6.2 Website Improvement

The website will continue to be updated on a regular basis. In addition, in every page in the website, social media buttons will be added so that the individuals who read an article can share it with their connections.

In addition, the newsletter will also be sent to the users automatically in their email when they add their email in the project's subscription list. Another improvement that will be made is that every month an article will be issued by the partners. The article will be written by a different partner on a rotation basis, on a content of their choice.

6.3 SafePASS Webinar

Following the travelling restrictions posed by the global Covid-19 pandemic, the SafePASS project is planning to organise its next international workshop in the form of a webinar. It will target academia, the maritime industry but also policy makers and government administrations. Although the specific date has not yet been confirmed, a suitable slot is investigated to avoid unnecessary overlapping with similar events related to passenger ship safety. It has been agreed that the time of the webinar should be such that it will allow attendance not only from European countries but also from the east coast of the United States where there is a clustering of significant stakeholders such as from the head offices of the Royal Caribbean Cruise Line and other large passenger ship operators. The organisation will follow the successful layout of the recent online Int. Conference on Ship & Offshore structures (ICSOS 2020) organised from 1st to 4th of September by the University of Strathclyde. It will have a single (plenary) session format, with several invited prominent keynote speakers and panel discussion at the end. The Zoom webinar tool will be used. Consecutive sessions will address different aspects of the passenger ship evacuation problem. Moderators will collect questions from the chat channel and pass them to the panel of each session. This will give room for a lively, informative, and constructive discussion.

6.4 Scientific Dissemination Opportunities

For the next period it is envisioned that more scientific papers will be published and disseminated through Research Gate platform, as the research output of the project will grow. Consortium partners will participate in more conferences and events and will publish scientific papers in renown journals.

6.4.1 Conferences and Professional Society Meetings

All consortium members have access to a live [Google Sheets document](#) where they can find potential dissemination and communication opportunities. The sheet is being updated on a regular basis and contains a list of conferences, symposiums and workshops that are related to the maritime industry. It is being a useful tool for keeping the SafePASS partners informed about events that they might be interested in attending and presenting their project related work. Due to COVID-19 many of the listed events were cancelled (e.g. TRA 2020, Posidonia 2020) but there are many more that will be held virtually this year and it is expected that consortium members will be present in some of them. In the table below you can find the most recently added events.

Table 11: Recently Added Dissemination and Opportunity Events

Date	Event	Location	Website	Important Info
------	-------	----------	---------	----------------

15/01/2020	Marine Design (MD2020) 2020	Cadiz, Spain	https://www.rina.org.uk/Marine_Design_2020.html	Abstract Deadline 30/09/2019
08/11/2019	Coastal Offshore and Ocean Engineering Conference (COO)	Gdansk, Poland	https://oio.pg.edu.pl/coo/home	Abstract Deadline 30/09/2019
20/04/2021	Ship Evacuation and Emergency Response Risk Modelling		https://www.sname.org/westerneurope/events/	
08/06/2021	A Discussion on Famous Spanish Naval Architects and Marine Engineers		https://www.sname.org/westerneurope/events/	
01/2021	Surveillance, Search, Rescue and Small Craft Conference	London, UK	https://www.rina.org.uk/cgi-bin/showpage.fcgi	
01/2021	FULL-Scale Ship Performance	TBC/ Online Conference	https://www.rina.org.uk/events_programme	
03/2021	Maritime innovation. emerging technologies	Online Conference	https://www.rina.org.uk/cgi-bin/showpage.fcgi	
05/2021	Design & Construction of Super & Mega Yachts	Italy	https://www.rina.org.uk/events_programme	
13-18/06/2021	1st International Conference on the Stability and Safety of Ships and Ocean Vehicles (STAB&S 2021)	Glasgow, Scotland	http://www.stab2021.org/	Abstract Deadline 15/10/2020
09/2021	ICCAS 2021	Japan	https://www.rina.org.uk/cgi-bin/showpage.fcgi	
5-8/10/2020	Sea Trade Cruise	Virtual	https://www.seatradecruiseevents.com/en/seatrade-cruise-virtual.html	
7-9/10/2020	NAVEXPRO	France	https://www.navexpo.com/en/the-exhibition/the-exhibition	
2-5/02/2021	SMM	Germany	https://www.smm-hambusrg.com/en/	

4-6/02/2021	ICORES 2021	Australia	http://www.icores.org/	Regular Paper submission 14 September, 2020. Doctoral Consortium Paper Submission: December 9, 2020
6-10/06/2022	Posidonia 2022	Greece	https://posidonia-events.com/	

7 Conclusions

The current report presented the dissemination and communication activities that were undertaken during the first year of the SafePASS H2020 project. It outlined the outreach events and activities that were held during the 1st year of the project's lifetime and presented a quantitative assessment of their effectiveness in raising awareness of the project's outcomes amongst all stakeholders, targeted communities, and eventually the general public.

Besides, this report with the information provided, detailed the events such as conferences, workshops, plenary meetings, and field trips organised by SafePASS, or which SafePASS partners attended and promoted the project's work and vision. Furthermore, the report portrayed the information regarding the project's social media footprint, the website and the publication of scientific papers, newsletters, and project-related information material. Regarding the platforms, audience insights and other performance monitoring data were provided, underlining the successful implementation of the SafePASS Dissemination and Communication Plan and its updates to face the arising challenges. Concluding, it can be also mentioned, that the project is in line with the stated KPIs, the stakeholders' expectations and the contractual obligations mentioned in the SafePASS Grant Agreement.

8 REFERENCES

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ANNEXES

Annex 1: Website Analytics

Table 12: Website Traffic: Viewers, Sessions and Unique Visitors by Country

Country	Page Views	Sessions	Unique Visitors
Greece	2,255	569	200
United Kingdom	1,572	398	142
United States	153	71	64
Italy	152	43	20
France	126	29	21
Spain	112	24	11
Denmark	107	25	13
Netherlands	80	20	12
Germany	74	32	23
Ireland	67	24	19
Sweden	51	17	8
Finland	49	22	11
Cyprus	28	11	9
Norway	26	12	10
Bulgaria	18	1	1
Portugal	14	5	5
Belgium	11	6	5
Canada	8	3	3
China	6	3	2
Philippines	5	3	3
India	5	5	5
South Africa	4	1	1
Bermuda	4	1	1
Turkey	3	2	2
Romania	3	2	2

Switzerland	2	1	1
South Korea	2	1	1
Serbia	2	1	1
Mexico	2	2	2
Israel	2	2	2
Australia	2	1	2
Argentina	2	2	2
Viet Nam	1	1	1
Croatia	1	1	1
Colombia	1	1	1
Austria	1	1	1
Aruba	1	1	1